

The morphological characterization of the sensilla on the antennae and mouthparts of *Camptopus tragacanthae* (Kolenati, 1845) (Hemiptera, Alydidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Camptopus tragacanthae* (Kolenati, 1845) (Hemiptera, Alydidae) is a species that belongs to the Aldidae family (Hemiptera) and its host plants are *Hypericum perforatum*, *Astragalus* sp. which are economically important. The sensilla are the main sensory organs of insects with their chemoreceptor, thermohygroreceptor or mechanoreceptor roles. They are located on the integument of antennae, head, mouthparts, legs or other body part of insects. The researchers can use sensilla as a taxonomical character because of the variation of the types, number, position, or distribution of them, so their structures should be enlightened. In accordance with this purpose, the sensilla structures on the mouthparts and antennae of male and female individuals of *C. tragacanthae* were examined with stereomicroscope and scanning electron microscope techniques in detail. **This study is the first morphological research on the sensilla of the genus *Camptopus*.** The antennae and mouthpart specimens were first photographed with a stereomicroscope, then cleaned for a scanning electron microscope, air-dried, covered with gold and examined. In the manner of our study, 3 major types of sensilla on the antennae (sensilla trichodea, sensilla basiconica, and sensilla coeloconica) and 2 major types of sensilla on the mouthparts (sensilla trichodea and sensilla basiconica) have been identified. While there are more sensilla on the antennae than the mouthparts, it can be said that the predominant sensilla type in both body parts is the sensilla trichodea.

KEY WORDS: Hemiptera, Heteroptera, insect, scanning electron microscopy, sensory organ.

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INTRODUCTION

The Alydidae family consists of species that are widely distributed in the world. The species belonging to this family have been identified by many researchers in various continents of the world, in various countries such as Papua New Guinea, America, Korea and Japan. It has been reported that these species, which have piercing-sucking mouth type, have economic importance especially on rice and soybean because they reduce yield, quality and seed viability (Sands, 1977; Brier & Rogers, 1991; Lee et al., 2004; Jung et al., 2005; Takeuchi, 2007; Hwang et al., 2022; Wilczek, 2022).

The Alydidae family is represented by 8 species in Turkey and one of them is *Camptopus tragacanthae* Kolenati, 1845 (Önder et al. 2006; Dursun et al. 2010; Çerçi and Koçak, 2017). *C. tragacanthae* is a widespread species that is distributed in Afghanistan, Anatolia, Azerbaijan, northwestern China, Georgia, Iran, Kazakhstan, southwestern Russia, Tadzhikistan, Transcaucasia, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan (Dolling, 2006; Dursun et al., 2010; Ghahari et al., 2010; Samin and Linnavuori, 2015). In Turkey, it is reported that it is in Ankara, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bursa, Elazığ, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Iğdır, Isparta, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Nevşehir, Sivas, and Tokat by several researchers (Kiritshenko, 1924; Pehlivan, 1981, Kiyak, 1990, 1993; Kiyak et al., 2004; Dursun, 2009; Dursun et al., 2010; Fent and Japoshvili, 2012; Çerçi et al., 2018; Yazıcı, 2022).

The host plants of *C. tragacanthae* are *Hypericum perforatum*, *Astragalus* sp. (Dursun et al., 2010). For instance, Kiyak (2019) reported that *Astragalus microcephalus* is the host plant of this insect species. Both *Hypericum perforatum* and *Astragalus* sp are of great economic importance as they are used as medicinal plants and/or ethnopharmacological agent and *C. tragacanthae* individuals on these plants endanger these species and allow yield reduction (Saddiqe et al.,

2010; Süntar et al., 2010; Berezutsky et al., 2023).

Sensilla act as chemo-receptors, thermo-hygroreceptors, and/or mechanoreceptors found on different regions of the body of insects in different densities. They have a great importance on finding mates or food, detecting volatile chemicals of air, physical and mechanical signals and other various functions about living. The distribution, types, sizes and densities of the sensilla show great variation among different insect species (Chapman, 1998; Isidoro et al., 2001; Akent'eva, 2008; Carey & Carlson, 2011; Fu et al., 2012; Brozek & Bourgoïn, 2013; Brozek & Zettel, 2014; Parveen et al., 2015; Cao & Huang, 2016; Nowinska & Brozek, 2017; Seada & Hamza, 2018; Tazsakowski et al., 2019; Faucheux et al., 2020; Freitas et al, 2020; Amutkan Mutlu et al., 2021; Giglio et al., 2022; Polat et al., 2021, 2022; Rani et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2023).

The main goal of our research is to reveal the morphological characteristically features of sensilla types on the mouth and antennae of *C. tragacanthae* which has an economical importance due to damage the *Hypericum perforatum* and *Astragalus* sp.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, the preserved samples of adult male and female *C. tragacanthae* as museum material were used.

The samples were collected in Hazar Lake, Elazığ province in 1985-1998 and were stored in Gazi University. First, the outer surface of the male and female insects was cleaned via ultrasonic cleaner. Then, the samples were air dried, were mounted on the SEM stubs and were coated with gold (Au) with sputter coater (Polaron SC502), observe in SEM (JEOL JSM 6060 LV). All the experiments were applied in Gazi University, Prof. Dr. Zekiye Suludere Electron Microscope Center and photographed (at 10-15 kV accelerating voltage).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SEM and stereomicroscopic observations that we made showed that, the mouth has a labrum and labium and the antennae has 4 segments in *C. tragacanthae*. The most common sensilla type in all these regions is sensilla trichodea (ST). This result shows parallelism with the study of Nowińska & Brożek (2021) and Polat et al. (2022)'s study. The predominant sensilla type in the examined samples of these species is ST that have many functions such as mechanoreceptors and chemoreceptors. For example, Nowińska & Brożek (2021) reported that the thick STs were olfactory sensilla while thin STs were chemosensilla of the antennae of *Plea minutissima* Leach, 1818 (Hemiptera, Pleidae).

Moreover, 2 other types of sensilla were also identified in different sizes; sensilla basiconica (SB), and sensilla coeloconica (SCo) in *C. tragacanthae*. When they are compared, it has been observed in studies that the number of sensilla in the antennae is higher than in the mouthparts similarly in *Notonecta viridis* Delcourt, 1909 (Hemiptera, Notonectidae) (Polat et al., 2021).

Sensilla on the antennae

There are two antennae with four segment of *C. tragacanthae* males and females (Fig. 1). Different types of sensilla was detected on every segment of antennae according to the results of this study. The densest segment in terms of the number of sensilla is the fourth antennal segment in the distal region.

The first antennal segment is close to the head and called proximal part. There are long and thin STs and the bottom parts of sensilla are swollen (Fig. 2). Besides, the SCo was also detected on the first segment of antennae of females (Fig. 2b).

The second, third segment of the antennae have mid-intensity ST. The bottom of the sensilla looks swollen (Fig. 3).

The fourth segment of the antennae has

ST and SCo in similar ways with the first segment. The sensilla type that dominates the images in all three segments is ST. However, the SCo are seen in a single row (Fig. 4).

The fourth segment in the distal region is the segment with the highest density and variety of sensilla compared to other segments. In this segment, in addition to ST and SCo, there is also SB. In SEM images of the fourth segment, it can be seen that there are two different type of SCo (Fig 5). Some researchers reported that the SB is related to perception of volatile plant compounds (Zhu et al., 2023).

Due to the role of male and female in mating, some sensilla structures and types may differ. However, no significant difference was observed in the sensilla types and distribution of female and male individuals of the examined species in this study.

Sensilla on the mouthparts

The insects belong to the order Hemiptera have the labrum (Lm), the labium (Lb), labial groove, and stylet fascicle as their mouthparts. Although the general structures of the insect species in this order are like this, they also have some similarities and differences in terms of sensilla distribution, number, type and/or sizes of sensilla (Wang et al., 2020; Amutkan Mutlu et al., 2021; Polat et al., 2021, 2022).

In male and female *C. tragacanthae* the mouthparts are consisted of Lm and Lb (Fig 6). The Lm is composed of single piece while the Lb is divided into 4 regions. The sensilla types and distributions on the mouthparts of female and male insects are generally very similar. In terms of parts of the mouthparts, segments of *C. tragacanthae* are, in general, similar to those of other members of the order Hemiptera such as *Physopelta gutta* (Burmeister, 1834) (Largidae), *Macrocheraia grandis* (Gray, 1832) (Largidae), *N.viridis*, *Aelia rostrata* Boh.

(Pentatomidae), *Dolycoris indicus* Stål, 1876 (Pentatomidae), *Eocanthecona furcellata* (Wolff) (Pentatomidae), *Perillus bioculatus* (F.) (Pentatomidae), *Piezodorus hybneri* (Gmelin, 1790) (Pentatomidae), and *Physopelta quadriguttata* Bergroth, 1894 (Largidae) (Parveen et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2019, 2020; Polat et al., 2021, 2022).

The labrum is located above the Lb-1 and looks like long and thin structure. While there is no sensilla on the surface in the proximal region of the labrum, sparsely arranged ST were detected on the middle and distal sides of the labrum of both males and females (Fig 6).

There are STs has on the surface of the first segment of the labium (Lb-1) in males and females. They are straight and middle size and they are arranged in a single row on both sides of the labrum. (Fig 7).

The predominant sensilla type on the second part of Lb is the medium-sized ST and is seen in very similar numbers and distribution in both males and females (Fig 8). However, there is a small symmetrical SB on the right and left near the region where Lb-2 meets Lb-1.

The third section of the Lb has short and middle size STs on its surface of the female *C. tragacanthae* (Fig 9). Some STs are straight while others are slightly curved. In males, only middle-sized STs were observed. Sensilla distribution on the Lb-3 is sparse in both sexes.

There are middle-sized STs arranged in two longitudinal rows in Lb-4 in female and male *C. tragacanthae* (Fig 10). There are some small SBs fused together at the tip of Lb-4 in males. This structure was not observed in females.

The insect sensilla are responsible for the vital activities of insect to survive and continue its lineage. Each types of sensilla in insects has divergent sensory duties as chemoreceptor, thermohygroreceptor, or mechanoreceptor. Insects achieve this, for example, by using their sensilla

trichodea as mechanoreceptors in finding food for nutrition or sensilla basiconica for movement of its mouthparts. The second important aspect in which sensilla function is their duties in finding a mate. They accomplish their task by finding volatiles such as pheromones in the air. The mouthparts of *C. tragacanthae* have few sensilla, but the majority of these sensilla are ST. For this reason, it can be said that *C. tragacanthae* mostly uses the mechanoreceptor pathway in finding food (Chapman, 1998; Carey & Carlson, 2011; Brozek & Zettel, 2014; Parveen et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2019; Amutkan Mutlu et al., 2021; Nowińska & Brożek, 2021; Polat et al., 2021; Rani et al., 2021).

Sensilla varieties, their density and distribution in the region of the mouthpart are related to the diet of these species. In other words, their sensilla are diversified and shaped according to their feeding habits.

The only important consideration when identifying sensilla species is their morphological structure. So, it is thought that the dissimilarity in morphological structure, quantity, distribution and etc. among different insect taxa and even the both sexes a species can be used as taxonomical characters due to it distinguishing significance (Ågren, 1978; van Baaren et al., 1999; Brożek, 2008; Nowińska & Brożek, 2021; Polat et al., 2021, 2022). In consequence of our study, two different types of sensilla were found on the mouthparts, mostly ST of three different sizes, while three kinds of sensilla were found on the antennae in *C. tragacanthae*. It can be thought that the high number and variety of sensilla in the antennae tells us that *C. tragacanthae* male and females receives a lot of stimuli from the environment.

With the results of this detailed scanning electron microscope study we have done, we hope to contribute to the literature on sensilla structures of insects and to help reveal the similarities and differences in the morphology of different insect species.

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Figure. 1. The general view and four segments of antennae of *C. tragacanthae* male and females. a, c: female antennae, b, d: male antennae. [Stereomicroscope images (a and b), SEM images (c and d)]

Figure. 2. The first segment of the antennae. a, b: female, c, d: male insect. Arrows: St, encircled: SCo (SEM images)

Figure 3. The second segment of the antennae. a, b: female, c, d: male insect. Arrows: St, (SEM images)

Figure 4. The third segment of the antennae. a, b, c: female, d, e, f: male insect. Arrows: SCo, arrowheads: St (SEM images)

Figure. 5. The fourth segment of the antennae. a, b, c: female, d, e, f: male insect. Black arrows: St, white arrows: SCo1, asterisk: SCo2, arrowheads: Sb (SEM images)

Figure. 6. The general view of labrum (Lm) and the first segment of labium (Lb) of female (a) and male (b) (SEM images)

Figure. 7. The Sts on the Lm (encircled) and the first segment of Lb (arrows). a: female, b: male (SEM images)

Figure. 8. The second segment of Lb with St (arrows) in both sexes and Sb (arrowhead) in males. a, b: female, c, d: male (SEM images)

Figure. 9. The third segment of Lb with St (arrows) in both sexes. a: female, b: male (SEM images)

Figure. 10. The fourth segment of Lb with St (arrows) in both sexes and Sb in males (encircled). a: female, b: male (SEM images)